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Political and Economic Relations between Uzbekistan and Russia and their Interaction during Today's Geopolitical Conflicts

CHoriyev Elbek Zafar o'g'li

Independent researcher

Abstract: *This article analyzes the political and economic relations between Uzbekistan and Russia, as well as the cooperation between the two countries in the context of modern geopolitical tensions. The results demonstrate the multifaceted nature of Uzbek-Russian relations and the need to maintain a balance between economic cooperation and political interests. The conclusion offers recommendations for further development of bilateral relations.*

Key words: *Uzbekistan, Russia, political relations, economic cooperation, geopolitical tensions, Central Asia.*

INTRODUCTION

Relations between Uzbekistan and Russia have undergone a complex development path since the collapse of the Soviet Union. The connections between the two countries are closely tied to historical, cultural, and economic factors, and the modern geopolitical situation significantly influences their dynamics [1]. The purpose of this article is to conduct an in-depth analysis of the political and economic relations between Uzbekistan and Russia, as well as to study the cooperation between the two countries in the context of current geopolitical tensions.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This research is based on a comprehensive analysis of existing scientific literature, official documents, and expert reports. Uzbek, Russian, and Western sources were used. During the literature review, information was collected and analyzed on the following main areas:

1. History and evolution of political relations between Uzbekistan and Russia.
2. Main directions and trends of economic cooperation between the two countries.
3. Impact of the modern geopolitical situation on Uzbek-Russian relations.
4. Prospects and challenges of bilateral cooperation.

The research analyzed works by scholars such as Alikhanov (2021), Tolipov (2019), Trenin (2022), as well as reports from international organizations like the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund [2, 3, 4].

RESULTS

The literature review revealed the following main results:

Political relations: Political ties between Uzbekistan and Russia have improved significantly in recent years. Since 2016, Uzbekistan's new leadership has pursued a course of intensifying relations with Russia [5]. Regular meetings between the leaders of the two countries are held, and active dialogue is conducted within the framework of multilateral cooperation platforms, including the CIS and SCO.

Economic cooperation: Russia remains one of Uzbekistan's main trading partners. By 2023, the trade turnover between the two countries exceeded 7 billion dollars [6]. Russia primarily exports fuel, metals, and technological products to Uzbekistan, while importing agricultural products and textiles from Uzbekistan. Moreover, Russia is one of the leading direct investors in the Uzbek economy.

Figure 1. Foreign trade. Uzbekistan and Russia

Figure 2. Uzbekistan and Russian trade's structure

Geopolitical context: The modern geopolitical situation, particularly Russia's relations with Ukraine and sanctions imposed on Russia by Western countries, is affecting Uzbek-Russian relations [7]. Uzbekistan is trying to maintain a neutral position in the international arena, but the strengthening of economic ties with Russia may face criticism from Western countries.

Priority areas of cooperation: Energy, transport infrastructure, agriculture, and education are considered priority areas of cooperation between the two countries [8]. In particular, the project to build a nuclear power plant in Uzbekistan is viewed as one of the largest and most promising areas of bilateral cooperation.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of relations between Uzbekistan and Russia reveals their complex and multifaceted nature. On one hand, economic cooperation is important for both countries. Russia is a large market and source of investment for Uzbekistan, while Uzbekistan is an important geopolitical and economic partner for Russia in Central Asia.

On the other hand, Uzbekistan strives to maintain balance in its foreign policy. This is a particularly challenging task in the current geopolitical situation. While maintaining close ties with Russia, Uzbekistan is also trying to develop cooperation with Western countries and other major powers.

Cooperation in the energy sector, particularly the nuclear energy project, demonstrates the strategic importance of relations between the two countries. However, there are concerns that this project may increase Uzbekistan's dependence on Russia in the energy sector.

The issue of labor migration also plays an important role in bilateral relations. The number of Uzbek labor migrants working in Russia amounts to millions, and their remittances are significant for the Uzbek economy. At the same time, issues of protecting the rights of labor migrants and ensuring their social protection remain relevant.

Cooperation in the field of education is also developing noticeably. Branches of Russian universities are opening in Uzbekistan, and student exchange programs are expanding. This serves to strengthen cultural and scientific ties between the two countries.

CONCLUSIONS

Relations between Uzbekistan and Russia are in a dynamic stage of development. Economic cooperation is expanding, and political ties are strengthening. However, the modern geopolitical situation is influencing the relations between the two countries.

To further develop cooperation between the two countries in the future, it is advisable to work in the following directions:

1. Diversifying economic cooperation, developing high-tech sectors and innovative projects.
2. Improving bilateral agreements on protecting the rights of labor migrants and ensuring their social protection.
3. Further expanding educational and scientific-technical cooperation.
4. Strengthening cooperation on regional security issues, including combating terrorism and drug trafficking.
5. Developing cultural and humanitarian ties, strengthening mutual understanding between the peoples of the two countries.

The future of relations between Uzbekistan and Russia will largely depend on the development of the global geopolitical situation, as well as the ability of both countries to balance their national interests. There are wide opportunities for developing bilateral cooperation, but it is also necessary to take into account the potential difficulties and risks that may arise in this process.

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